

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

USING GREEN WALNUT REMAINS TO GET A FUNCTIONAL PRODUCT

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Abstract

The nature of Georgia is rich in raw materials for the production of alcoholic beverages – plants. Based on this, the production of dessert liqueurs using existing raw materials is a very topical issue. The rest of the green walnut was chosen as the object of study, since it is characterized by a high content of biologically active compounds. The presented work shows that in the case of using invert sugar, the hydrolysis of substances is significantly reduced, which is to some extent associated with a high concentration of glucose; At the same time, the nutritional purpose is improved by the use of invert sugar. The addition of stevioside and low concentration alcohol reduces calories.

Keywords: green walnut, functional product, alcoholic beverages, stevia plant (*Stevia Rebaudiana Bertoni*)

Preserving human health and prolonging life is an important task of the country, which is associated with the use of products containing biologically necessary substances.

Nutrition and health requirements have been developed by the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union (EC1924/2006; EU2012/12) specifying a number of substances that play a specific physiological role. Particular attention is paid to the content of antioxidant substances.

When developing technology, one should take into account the recommendations of the World Health Organization (WHO, 2003) and the requirements of the European regulation (EC1924/2006), according to which it is necessary to significantly limit sugar consumption. In recent years, much attention has been paid to the use of stevioside as a sweetener.

The purpose of the research is to obtain a relatively low-calorie dessert liqueur of a new type using the residue of vegetable raw materials, without sucrose, while preserving biologically active substances. The product preparation procedures are based on traditional technologies, but include elements of innovation.

- Stevioside is used (a sweetener, a glycoside derived from the stevia plant (*Stevia Rebaudiana Bertoni*), a honey-sweet plant that does not contain carbohydrates. It has antihyperglycemic, insulinotropic, anticarcinogenic effects [1-5].

- A recipe for invert sugar from sucrose has been developed, temperature, exposure and ratio of components have been determined.

- The technological parameters for the preparation of dessert liqueur have been determined.

Research methodology - the green peel of a walnut was chosen as the object of research, which was used to prepare a dessert liquor [6]. Green walnuts are distinguished by a high content of biologically active compounds. Maintaining their stability is very important while improving nutritional value.

Unripe green walnuts contain protein, fats, organic (malic, citric) acids, carotene, phenolic acids, tannins (14-35%), ascorbic acid up to 2%, quinones: σ - and β -juglone, as well as water-soluble and fat-soluble vitamins, carbohydrates, iodine, micro and macro elements.

Green walnuts contain 9 times more vitamin C than blackcurrants and 50 times more than citrus fruits. Its amount increases as the fruit develops and reaches a maximum (2.5%) during the growing season – when the fruit is immature. It is known that ascorbic acid causes the synthesis of deoxyribonucleic acid. Participates in redox processes, in the synthesis and metabolism of thyroid hormones and thyroid hormones of the adrenal glands. Green walnut exhibits phytocidal, antimicrobial properties, releases aromatic substances and essential oils, has a medical (healing) effect. Green walnut reaches its maximum positive properties from mid-May to early June. [7].

A semi-finished product for obtaining liquor was prepared on the basis of a double extraction. The scheme below shows the parameters, the alcohol content (vol.%) and the ratio to the feedstock. I extraction – duration 15 days, II extraction – 10 days [8].

Technological scheme for the production of semi-finished products

Invert sugar is used instead of sucrose for the preparation of liquor, on the basis of which 80% of sugar is inverted, the total amount of sugar is 70%, invert sugar is 57%, sucrose is 13%. Stevioside 0.8-1.0 g/l is added to the resulting syrup.

In the semi-finished product obtained from the waste of walnut greens, invert sugar syrup is added in a ratio of 5: 1, where the amount of invert sugar is 8%, and sucrose – 2%. The main attention was paid to the sugar content in the object (Table 1).

Table 1.

Qualitative sugar content in liquor g/100g

object	invert sugar	simple sugar	sucrose	calories		kcal	
				With technology	existing	With technology	new
Green nut liqueur	8.0	3.0	2.0	120		52	

As a result of research, it has been shown that in the case of using inverted sugar, the hydrolysis of substances is significantly reduced, which is to some extent associated with a high concentration of glucose; At the same time, the nutritional purpose is improved by the use of invert sugar. The addition of stevioside and low concentration alcohol reduces calories.

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